

Teaching Performance of Beginning Teachers in Ilocos Sur: Basis for New Educators' Support and Training Program

Katrina Joy A. Naval, EdD

St. Paul College of Ilocos Sur

ABSTRACT: Using Mixed Methods Sequential Explanatory design, this study determined the teaching performance of beginning teachers of schools run by the Sisters of St. Paul of Chartres Education Ministry (SPCEM) in Ilocos Sur. Moreover, emerging themes from semi-structured interviews were used as basis of strategies included in the induction program. Majority of the respondents are females, licensed, residing in rural areas, and State University graduates. On teaching performance, the beginning teachers were rated "Very Satisfactory". Emerging themes were sharing of best practices and words of affirmation; focused observations with focused feedback; Reflective Teaching; and Provision of learning resources and materials.

KEYWORDS: beginning teachers, induction program, teaching performance, mixed methods

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of aligning a Teacher Induction Program to the professional standards for teachers is highlighted in the Teacher Professional Development Case Studies by the Asia Development Bank released in July 2021. Beginning teachers are expected to show good professional practice, encompassing their ability to translate professional knowledge into practice (Manasia, et.al 2019). A welldeveloped induction program or faculty development program can help them apply pedagogical knowledge into practice.

The need for an induction program stems from the challenges that these teachers face early on in their careers. Beginning or probationary teachers experience several difficulties, especially in pedagogy. (Estrera, 2019); (Antipolo and Rogayan, 2021); (Araneta, 2021); and (Dela Cruz, 2019). Among the primarily identified difficulties are lesson planning and assessment, lack of technical expertise in the utilization of appropriate tools for assessing students' authentic learning, and workload challenges. Moreover, pedagogy, classroom management, and school location challenges were also identified as problems although these were not extremely experienced.

With this, it was recommended that school administrators should coach and scaffold all newly hired teachers to improve their teaching competence. Thus, along with the national adoption of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, the Department of Education launched initiatives to stratify the classroom appraisal tools used depending on the career stage of the teachers. The classroom observation required in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers-Results-Based Performance Management System (PPST-RPMS) has "become more objective and standardized, and is used for mentoring, coaching, performance review and evaluation which supports the teachers' on-going professional development." Unfortunately, the use of the PPST-RPMS is limited to the Department of Education teachers, and only teachers serving in DepEd are the ones included in the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers.

While there are studies that determined the relationship between teacher induction and performance, (Padillo et al., 2021); (Nicodemus, 2011); (Munshi, 2018); (Sayomac 2018); and (Araneta, 2021); as well as experiences of teachers in their beginning years, (Antipolo & Rogayan, Jr., 2021); (Quimque, 2020), (de Vera, 2021); and (Peria, 2019), there is a limited number of literature focusing on developing an induction program that is anchored on the domains of PPST for private school teachers in Paulinian schools. Moreover, there is limited literature on using the teaching performance results of teachers in private schools to develop an induction program for beginning teachers.

This study therefore, determined the teaching performance of beginning teachers from the Grade School and High School departments of Sisters of St. Paul of Chartres Education Ministry member schools in Ilocos Sur using an appraisal tool for classroom instruction anchored on the domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. Moreover, the teaching performance of the beginning teachers served as the basis for developing the NEST Program or the New Educators' Support and Training Program.

Teaching Performance of Beginning Teachers in Ilocos Sur: Basis for New Educators' Support and Training Program

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Research Design

This study utilized Mixed Methods Approach specifically the Sequential Explanatory Design which consists of two distinct phases: quantitative followed by qualitative to provide a better understanding of the problem and complex phenomenon rather than using only one approach (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2007). In here, data collection starts with the quantitative phase followed by the qualitative phase to explain or expand on quantitative results (Creswell, Plano Clark, et.al., 2003).

In this study, therefore, the quantitative data collection and analysis phase included the assessment of the teaching performance of the beginning teachers using a researcher-constructed and validated Appraisal Tool for Classroom Instruction. The areas in the appraisal tool were aligned to the domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers namely: curriculum and planning; content knowledge and pedagogy; learning environment; assessment and reporting; diversity of learners; and personal qualities. The validated tool was used by the Subject Team Leaders and/or Academic Coordinators in assessing the teaching performance of the respondents. Triangulation was observed in determining the teaching performance by getting the mean of their appraisal rating from their direct head's evaluation, Academic Coordinator's evaluation, and selfevaluation. However, for St. William's Institute and St. Joseph's Institute, the organizational structure only includes one direct head of the faculty due to the number of enrollees and the number of faculty. For St. William's Institute, only the Academic Coordinators serve as the direct head of the beginning teachers while for St. Joseph's Institute, the direct head of the beginning teachers are the Subject Area Coordinators.

The teaching performance of the beginning teachers was statistically analyzed using mean and the norms for interpretation were as follows:

Statistical Range	Item Descriptive Rating	Overall Descriptive Rating
4.21 – 5.00	Exceeds Expectations	Outstanding
3.41 – 4.20	Meets Expectations	Very Satisfactory
2.61 – 3.40	Partially Meets Expectations	Satisfactory
1.81 – 2.60	Hardly Meets Expectations	Poor
1.00 - 1.80	Does Not Meet Expectations	Very Poor

Moreover, the correlation between the profile of the beginning teachers and their teaching performance was statistically analyzed using simple linear correlation.

The qualitative phase included the conduct of semistructured interviews with the respondents from each participating school to present the findings. The researcher used a priori codes in formulating the guide questions for the semi-structured interviews. Thus, since the focus of the study is on the development of a program for beginning teachers, the semi-structured interviews aimed to confirm the needs of the respondents based on the results of their teaching performance evaluation and served as added basis in the development of the induction program. The developed program underwent validation on these areas: (a) focus on content; (b) incorporation of active learning and utilization of adult learning theory; (c) support on collaboration; (d) use of modeling of effective practice; (e) provision of coaching and expert support; (f) adequate opportunities for feedback and reflection; and (g) sustained duration.

2.3. Respondents/Participants

Total enumeration was used by including all the beginning teachers from the Grade School and High School with 0 to 3 years of teaching experience employed at SPCEM-member schools in Ilocos Sur namely: St. Paul College of Ilocos Sur (SPCIS), St. William's Institute (SWI), and St. Joseph Institute (SJI) for SY 2022-2023 as the respondents of the study. In total, there were 21 respondents from SPCIS, 12 FROM SWI, and 21 from SJI.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following tables present the quantitative data obtained in the first phase of the study:

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Profile	School 1		School 2		School 3		As a whole	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Sex								
Male	1	8.33	9	42.86	3	14.29	13	24.07
Female	11	91.67	12	57.14	18	85.71	41	75.93
Total	12	100.00	21	100.00	21	100.00	54	100.00
Qualification								
Non-licensed	1	8.33	11	52.38	1	4.76	13	24.07
Licensed	11	91.67	10	47.62	20	95.24	41	75.93

Teaching Performance of Beginning Teachers in Ilocos Sur: Basis for New Educators' Support and Training Program

Total	12	100.00	21	100.00	21	100.00	54	100.00
Place of Residence								
Urban	0	0.00	2	9.52	4	19.05	6	11.11
Rural	12	100.00	19	90.48	17	80.95	48	88.89
Total	12	100.00	21	100.00	21	100.00	54	100.00
Type of School Graduated From								
Private HEI	2	16.67	7	33.33	3	14.29	12	22.22
SUC	10	83.33	14	66.67	18	85.71	42	77.78
Total	12	100.00	21	100.00	21	100.00	54	100.00

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, qualification, place of residence, and type of school graduated from. As seen in Table 2, the majority of the beginning teachers (41 or 75.93%) are female. On the other hand, thirteen (24.07%) of them are male. Moreover, majority of the beginning teachers (41 or 75.93%) are licensed, while thirteen (24.07%) are non-licensed. In terms of place of residence, most beginning teachers (48 or 88.89%) reside in rural areas, while six (11.11%) reside in urban areas. Lastly, a great majority of the beginning teachers (42 or 77.78%) graduated from a State University or College (SUC). Only twelve (22.22%) graduated from Private Higher Education Institutions (PHEIs).

Table 2. Overall Teaching Performance of the Beginning Teachers

Indicators	School 1		School 2		School 3		As a whole	
	M	DR	M	DR	M	DR	M	DR
Curriculum and planning	3.92	VS	3.77	VS	3.93	VS	3.88	VS
Content knowledge & pedagogy	3.96	VS	3.70	VS	3.90	VS	3.85	VS
Learning environment	3.90	VS	3.72	VS	3.94	VS	3.85	VS
Assessment and reporting	3.92	VS	3.54	VS	3.82	VS	3.76	VS
Diversity of learners	3.94	VS	3.65	VS	3.96	VS	3.85	VS
Personal qualities	4.20	VS	4.05	VS	4.24	O	4.17	VS
OVERALL	3.97	VS	3.74	VS	3.97	VS	3.89	VS

Legend:

Mean Range	Overall Descriptive Rating
4.21 – 5.00	Outstanding (O)
3.41 – 4.20	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2.61 – 3.40	Satisfactory (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Poor (P)
1.00 – 1.80	Very Poor (VP)

Table 2 shows the overall teaching performance of the beginning teachers. It can be gleaned from the table that the beginning teachers in the SPCEM schools obtained an overall mean of 3.89, described as “Very Satisfactory.” It is also significant to note that among all the domains, personal qualities obtained the highest mean rating of 4.17 described as “Very Satisfactory.” In contrast, assessment and reporting obtained the lowest rating with 3.76, described as “Very Satisfactory.”

The findings show that although the beginning teachers have a very satisfactory teaching performance in all the areas, there can still be added interventions or mentoring for them to demonstrate outstanding performance eventually. The high ratings on their teaching performance can also be attributed to the fact that the class observations were done in the last quarter of the school year, wherein coaching has presumably occurred within the year.

Teaching Performance of Beginning Teachers in Ilocos Sur: Basis for New Educators' Support and Training Program

Table 3. Relationship between the Profile of the Beginning Teachers and Their Teaching Performance

Profile	Statistics	Indicators						Overall
		A	B	C	D	E	F	
Sex	r-value	-0.140	-0.250	-0.155	-0.101	-0.184	-0.053	-0.174
	p-value	0.313	0.068	0.262	0.466	0.183	0.703	0.208
Qualification	r-value	-0.002	0.050	0.085	0.075	0.118	0.204	0.102
	p-value	0.987	0.718	0.541	0.588	0.396	0.140	0.465
Place of Residence	r-value	0.050	-0.001	-0.055	0.083	0.042	-0.010	0.024
	p-value	0.722	0.997	0.690	0.552	0.765	0.945	0.865
Type of School Graduated From	r-value	.310*	.344*	0.259	.379**	.381**	0.089	.352**
	p-value	0.023	0.011	0.058	0.005	0.004	0.524	0.009

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 shows the relationship between the profile of the beginning teachers and their teaching performance.

The type of school graduated from of the beginning teachers is significantly related to their overall teaching performance as supported by the r-value of 0.352.

Similarly, it is also significantly related to each of the six indicators. This finding implies that beginning teachers who graduated from SUCs tend to perform better than those who graduated from private HEIs.

The high teaching performance of the beginning teachers who mostly came from SUCs and LUCs, can be attributed to the qualifications of their professors at the tertiary level, specifically in their professional education courses and major courses. This finding supports the study of Balanquit, Ladia, and Nool (2023), who analyzed the correlation between faculty qualifications and board performance of their students. They discovered that HEIs with a higher number of faculty with post-baccalaureate degrees had higher board examination passing rates than those HEIs with a lesser number of faculty with master's or doctorate degrees.

On Induction Program for Beginning Teachers

Based on the assessment of the beginning teachers' teaching performance, and the result of the semistructured interviews conducted with the beginning teachers, the following emerged as themes from which the strategies and activities in the New Educators' Support and Training Program: *provision of materials, reflective teaching, sharing of best practices, and focused observation with focused feedback.*

A. Provision of Materials

The beginning teachers, especially those handling Religious Education subjects, expressed the need to be provided with materials since they are just starting to get familiar with the teaching-learning process. Moreover, the mandated integration of the Paulinian Core Values and Outcome-Based Education framework is difficult on their part considering their background as state university graduates who were trained with lesson plan formats following that of DepEd.

"Very challenging. As you know we do not have a consistent STL tapos wala pa kaming materials [we do not have materials]. What I used were my materials in college kaya what I do is to roam around all the subject areas to ask for help." P10

It should be noted that newly-hired teachers face several struggles in their careers, but most of them are related to their instructional delivery. The study by Araneta (2021) highlighted the challenge faced by new teachers regarding the "lack of instructional materials and facilities". The emphasis made by five respondents in the study is that it is difficult for the newly-hired teachers to teach because they are not familiar with the new curriculum at the same time, coupled with a lack of instructional materials.

B. Reflective Teaching

The beginning teachers recognize the importance of knowing the indicators in the tool used for evaluating their teaching performance even at the start of the school year:

"Before I was observed, I was able to see na kailangan pala i-integrate yung lesson dun sa ibang lessons na nabigay na in the past (Before I was observed, I was able to see that I need to integrate my current lesson to other lessons given in the past), like those lessons that were given in first quarter or second quarter. Because of that [knowing the indicators in the tool] I was able to apply it when I was observed, and that was even mentioned by my STL" P13

"Makakatulong po na alam namin kung saan kami i-observe para alam naming kung saan magfo-focus sa pagimprove sa pagtuturo namin". (It would really be helpful if we know the areas where we will be observed so that we know which areas to focus on in improving our teaching.) P3

Teaching Performance of Beginning Teachers in Ilocos Sur: Basis for New Educators' Support and Training Program

The beginning teachers affirmed that being aware of the indicators makes them see other elements of teaching that they need to do in their classes. However, one of the participants expressed her disagreement by pointing out that if teachers know the indicators, they will tend to focus on that area only, whereas being unaware of the indicators forces them to deliver well in all areas of teaching. A high-quality and functional induction program, as well as self-reflective dialogue with mentors and colleagues, allows beginning teachers to have a repertoire of effective practices, which in turn allows them to feel successful. Merely conversing with more experienced teachers who act as mentors can help in developing habits of inquiry, which can help in providing students with meaningful learning experiences.

C. Sharing of Best Practices

As beginning teachers, the respondents explained that they have varied understanding of the Paulinian Core Values, which made it difficult for them to use in their lessons. Since they are new to the institution, they recommended having a thorough orientation of the core values to have a common understanding of it.

“My idea of the core values like for example Christ-centeredness and charism, they are different and I base it on my perspective as a graduate of theology. They should orient us about the core values and explain to us what they mean.” P10

“Yes, Ma’am. Hindi naman namin maiintindihan agad ang ibig sabihin ng mga core values kaya ituro dapat sa amin kung paano. (We cannot immediately understand what the core values mean so they should be taught to us.) P3

These findings are supported by the profile of the beginning teachers since a great majority of them finished their tertiary education at State Universities or Colleges or at Local Universities or Colleges with a different culture and context from private schools. The difficulty of beginning teachers on providing activities or learning experiences for gospel or value integration can also be attributed to the context of the learning plan format taught to them in college. In their teaching internship course as pre-service teachers in SUCs and LUCs, they follow the DepEd lesson plan format, which does not include values integration. This experience causes difficulty for fresh graduates once they begin their teaching career in a private Catholic school.

The responses of the beginning teachers and their need to be mentored support the findings of Hadi (2015), who found out that although the teachers in selected high schools in Indonesia were able to choose the values they included in their lesson plans, they still had doubts about integrating such values into their lessons. Moreover, they concentrated on their materials too much, so they forgot about these values.

D. Focused Observation with Focused Feedback

Aside from sharing best practices, all the respondents from the SPCEM schools affirmed the importance of class observations in letting them learn about pedagogies and assessments. The number of class observations beginning teachers receive is also a factor affecting their confidence in class. Having several class observations within the year gives a sense of confidence and ease on the part of the beginning teachers.

“Everything seems normal, Ma’am. Wala ng kaba.” (Everything seems normal, Ma’am. We did not feel nervous anymore.) P4

This finding supports the finding of Suparto (2020), as cited by Barrogo (2020), that objective and standardized classroom observation, and academic supervision of classroom observation techniques, can help improve the quality of teaching-learning.

Considering both points shared by the respondents, mentors and direct heads of beginning teachers must present all the domains or areas that serve as the basis for evaluating their teaching performance. The process of class observations, as well as the tool used to evaluate them, must be explained clearly in the orientation phase, before the start of the school year. However, to have a more focused way of mentoring, informal class observations can be used to observe one specific domain only; until the beginning teacher has been observed informally several times within the school year, addressing all the domains in the tool. Once the informal observations are complete, the mentor or direct head can conduct a formal class observation on the teacher, focusing on all domains. Upon confirming the needs of the beginning teachers based on the emerging themes from the semistructured interviews, the researcher developed the New Educators' Support and Training Program with the following components: (I) rationale; (II) General Objectives; (III) Scope; (IV) Definition of Terms; (V) Framework; (VI) Process Matrix; and (VII) Monitoring and Evaluation.

Figure 1 shows the framework of the New Educators' Support and Training Program:

Teaching Performance of Beginning Teachers in Ilocos Sur: Basis for New Educators' Support and Training Program

Figure 1: New Educators' Support and Training

(NEST) Program Framework

The NEST framework presents the number of years of teaching service of beginning teachers. The number of years is represented by circles with varied sizes, signifying that the beginning teachers in their 3rd year of teaching experience have gained the most skills and competencies in their career. Moreover, each number of year is represented by a color which would predominantly appear in the program matrix for easier identification and color coding of the beginning teachers belonging to a certain number of years. The entire framework is circular because the repeated cycle of focused observation followed by focused feedback, which in turn results in improved teaching performance, is repeated in all the indicators and domains. The induction process must not end at one point: it must be implemented continuously until the beginning teachers are equipped and ready to proceed to the next career stage. Thus, the arrow at the middle signifies the exit point of the beginning teacher from the induction program once they manifest all teacher quality standards of a beginning teacher. The framework rests upon a nest to symbolize the sheltering and nurturing nature of the program.

To fully realize the components of the framework, the NEST Program will follow a process matrix consisting of the following: indicators from the appraisal tool for classroom instruction, indicators from the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, Strategies and Activities (varying depending on number of years), and evaluation or remarks.

The matrix serves as a guide to the mentor as to the strategies and activities which can be done to address an indicator from the Appraisal Tool for Classroom Instruction where the beginning teacher was observed to need help or focus on. The second column consists of the indicators from the Philippine Professional Standards of Teachers aligned with the indicators in the appraisal tool used in classroom observation.

On Validation of Developed Induction Program

The New Educators' Support and Training Program for beginning teachers underwent validation by specialists (all Doctorate holders in educational management) from varied fields and perspectives: (1) from the Schools Division of Ilocos Sur heading the Schools Governance and Operations Division office); (2) Program Chairperson of the Department of Arts and Sciences and Teacher Education; (3) Director of Planning and Quality Assurance of a private Catholic institution; (4) School Principal of an Archdiocesan school; and (5) a Master Teacher in a DepEd school.

Validating the program was based on (a) focus on content; (b) incorporation of active learning and utilization of adult learning theory; (c) support on collaboration; (d) use of modeling of effective practice; (e) provision of coaching and expert support; (f) adequate opportunities for feedback and reflection; and (g) sustained duration. The level of validity was categorized into Highly Valid, Valid, and Not Valid.

All the validators consider the NEST Program to address the set criteria, especially on focus on content, incorporation of active learning and utilization of adult learning theory, support on collaboration, adequate opportunities for feedback and reflection, and sustained duration which, all obtained a rating of 3.0 described as "Highly Valid."

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Majority of the beginning teachers in SPCEM schools in Ilocos Sur are female and licensed, residing in rural areas and graduated from a state university or college. The teaching performance of the beginning teachers is very satisfactory in terms of curriculum and planning, content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, assessment and reporting, diversity of learners, and personal

Teaching Performance of Beginning Teachers in Ilocos Sur: Basis for New Educators' Support and Training Program

qualities. Moreover, type of school graduated of the beginning teachers is significantly related to their overall teaching performance, and is also significantly related to each of the six indicators, which means that beginning teachers who graduated from SUCs tend to perform better than those who graduated from private HEIs.

The emerging themes drawn from the responses of the beginning teachers in their semi-structured interviews were: Sharing of best practices and words of affirmation; Focused observations with focused feedback; Reflective Teaching; and Provision of learning resources and materials which indicate that the beginning teachers find a direct and focused mentoring more needed than training or seminars.

With these findings, school administrators of the participating schools may implement New Educators' Support and Training Program for the beginning teachers in the incoming school year with an emphasis on explaining the Paulinian Core Values since most of the beginning teachers mostly come from SUCs. Also, the validated appraisal tool for classroom instruction may be used twice: at the beginning of the school year before the NEST Program is conducted and toward the end of the school year after the program is implemented to see any significant differences in the teachers' performance.

The Subject Team Leaders and Academic Coordinators may conduct staggered informal class observations that focus on a specific domain within the school year before evaluating the teaching performance of the beginning teachers at the end of the school year.

A follow-up study may be conducted after implementing the program, which may focus on either of the following: evaluation of the induction program vis a vis the teaching performance of the faculty, lived experiences of the beginning teachers and the mentors, or looking into the influence of mentoring on the novice teachers.

REFERENCES

- 1) Manasia, L.; Ianos, M.G.; Chicioeanu, T.D. Pre-service teacher preparedness for fostering education for sustainable development: an empirical analysis of central dimensions of teaching readiness. *Sustainability* 2020, 12, 166. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12010166>.
- 2) Estrera, R. (2019). The challenges encountered by the newly-hired teachers in the public secondary schools: basis for coaching. *Academia*. https://www.academia.edu/39994598/THE_CHALLENGES_ENCOUNTERED_BY_THE_NEWLY_HIRED_TEACHERS_IN_THE_PUBLIC_SECONDARY_SCHOOLS_BASIS_FOR_COACHING
- 3) Antipolo, A. M. R., & Rogayan, D. V. Jr. (2021). Filipino prospective teachers' experiences in teaching in K12 science curriculum: A crosssectional research. *JPBI (Jurnal Pendidikan Biologi Indonesia)*, 7(1), 1-10. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1298068.pdf>
- 4) Araneta, M., EdD. (2021). Induction program for beginning and experienced teachers: challenges and perspectives. *European modern studies journal*, 5(2). <https://journalems.com/index.php/emsj/article/view/235>
- 5) Dela Cruz, D. (2019). Effectiveness of class observation to the performance of teachers in public elementary school in the division of Antipolo. *International Journal of Engineering Science and Computing*, 9(3). [https://ijesc.org/upload/a20932cc0fcb12dbd2d1564cb6506b96.Effectiveness%20of%20Class%20Observation%20to%20the%20Performance%20of%20Teachers%20in%20Public%20Elementary%20School%20in%20the%20Division%20of%20Antipolo%20\(4\).pdf](https://ijesc.org/upload/a20932cc0fcb12dbd2d1564cb6506b96.Effectiveness%20of%20Class%20Observation%20to%20the%20Performance%20of%20Teachers%20in%20Public%20Elementary%20School%20in%20the%20Division%20of%20Antipolo%20(4).pdf)
- 6) Padillo, G. G., Manguilimotan, R. P., Capuno, R. G., & Espina, R. C. (2021). Professional development activities and teacher performance. *International Journal of Education and Practice*. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.18488/journal.61.2021.93.497.506>
- 7) Nicodemus, J. (2016). induction program, performance, and morale of teachers in selected schools in DepEd, Cavite City. *www.academia.edu*. https://www.academia.edu/26684357/INDUCTION_PROGRAM_PERFORMANCE_AND_MORALE_OF_TEACHERS_IN_SELECTED_SCHOOLS_IN_DEPED_CAVITE_CITY
- 8) Munshi, A. Induction programs, teacher efficacy, and inquiry practices in novice teachers. (2018). Dissertations. 18. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31979/etd.pk8d-cyvt> https://scholarworks.sjsu.edu/etd_dissertations/18
- 9) Sayomac, R. S. (2018). Effectiveness of induction program and performance of teachers in public schools in Davao City. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=13689>
- 10) Quimque, P. L. (2020). Lived experiences of newly hired teachers: basis for policy recommendations. *JPAIR Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=15130>
- 11) De Vera, R. (2021). Transitional experiences of newly hired teachers in department of education. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications*. <http://ijmrapp.com/wpcontent/uploads/2021/05/IJMRAP-V3N11P52Y21.pdf>

Teaching Performance of Beginning Teachers in Ilocos Sur: Basis for New Educators' Support and Training Program

- 12) Peria, A. T., & Torres, B. R. R. (2019). Aspects of classroom lived experiences of newly-hired teachers. *Asian Scientific Journals*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.7828/Ijher.v15i2.1323>
- 13) Creswell, J. W., Plano Clark, V. L., Gutmann, M. L., & Hanson, W. E. (2003). Advanced mixed methods research designs. *Handbook of mixed methods in social and behavioral research*, 209(240), 209-240.
- 14) Balanquit, E. P., Ladia, M. A. P., Embesan, S. A., & Legaspi, Y. S. (2018). The effect of remediation on the performance in retention examination of underachieving prospective secondary teachers. *The Upland Farm Journal*, 25(1), 15-28.
- 15) Araneta, M., EdD. (2021). Induction program for beginning and experienced teachers: challenges and perspectives. *European modern studies journal*, 5(2). <https://journalems.com/index.php/emsj/article/view/235>
- 16) Hadi, Rizali. 2015 The Integration of character values in the teaching of economics: a case of selected high schools in Banjarmasin. *International Education Studies*; Vol. 8, No. 7; 2015. doi:10.5539/ies.v8n7p11
- 17) Barrogo, S. (2020). Teachers' perception of standardized classroom observation tool. *International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research*.